

CHOLPON - FIREFIGHTER

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Annotation: This article provides information about the life and work of Abdulhamid Cholpon, a poet from Andijan, who entered Uzbek poetry in the 1920s like lightning. In Cholpon's poetry, the interests of the people and the Motherland are paramount. The talented poet fell victim to the repressive policies of the dictatorial Soviet regime.

Keywords: merchant-bazzoz, Foiqa, NKVD, mudarris, rus-tuzem school, Ulfat, sak, GPU.

Abdulhamid Sulaymon oglu Cholpon is one of the brightest intellectuals in the Uzbek literature and history of the 20th century. The real name of the fiery poet is Abdulhamid Suleiman's son, Cholpon is his nickname. Cholpon was born in 1897 in Qatortarak mahalla of Andijan city of Fergana region. Cholpon's father, Suleimanqul Muhammadyunus' son, was a well-known merchant. Sulaymonqul is also a creative person and wrote comic poems under the pseudonym "Rasvo". Cholpon's mother, Aisha Aya, was illiterate but was able to instill a love of science in her children. Aisha had fourteen children, but only four of them survived. Abdulhamid was the eldest child of this family and became the brother of his sisters Komila (1902), Fozila (1905) and Foiqa (1908) who were born after him [2, 9].

The exact date of the poet's birth is not known, but his sister, Foiqa Aya, said that her brother was a mucha sak and was four years old when the Andijan earthquake struck in 1902 [3, 8].

Cholpon's Andijan contemporary, the poet Ulfat, also states that he was born in 1898, but Cholpon was interviewed by V. Yan and filled out special questionnaires in the NKVD prison. year of birth.

Cholpon's father initially wanted his son to become a teacher and taught him at a madrassa in Andijan. Cholpon writes in his autobiography: "But instead of teaching, I decided to become an Uzbek writer, went to Tashkent, where I wrote poems, stories and sent them to magazines".

The young poet first studied at the Abdulhamid Madrasa (1908-1912) and then at the Russian-style school (1912-1914). He increased his literary, socio-political knowledge by reading the works of classical poets of the East and observing the Jadid press.

Cholpon has grown into a versatile artist, poet, writer, playwright, translator, critic and public figure.

Cholpon's career began in 1913-1914 with reports on the social and cultural life of Andijan. Meeting Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhonov and Ubaydulla Khojayev in Tashkent in 1914 was an important factor in the formation of Cholpon as a representative of the national revival movement. As a result, Yunusov's first creative steps were taken, simply informing him about life in Andijan.

Cholpon's first published work was the poem "To our Turkestan brothers" published in the newspaper "Sadoi Turkiston" on April 18, 1914 under the signature of "Abdulhamid Sulaymoni" [4, 425].

Although Abdulhamid Suleimani's name appeared frequently in the press in the 1920s, the first articles about him appeared in the early 1920s. The first of these articles was a review of the first collection of poems by the Tatar writer Zarif Bashiri (1888 - 1962) in the newspaper "Turkiston" on May 4, 1923, "Awakening". In 1925, Abdullah Qadiri also wrote about Cholpon.

In 1919, Cholpon worked for such newspapers as Yangi Sharq (Tashkent), from 1921 to 1922 for Akhboriy Bukhara (Bukhara), and in 1923 for Darkhan (Andijan). From 1924 to 1926, he published three books of poetry: "Awakening", "Springs", "Secrets of Dawn".

Cholpon was active from 1923 to 1937. He has created a number of collections of poetry, stories, plays, works: "Awakening", "Springs", "Secrets of Dawn", "Word", "Jor", "Sacrifice" Stories such as "Ignorance", "Doctor Muhammadiyor", "Moonlit nights", "Tulip in the snow", "Baker girl", "White king's gift", "Pearl", "Mushtumzo", "O Karshibaev", "Attack" (in collaboration with V.Yan), "Bright" (play), "Night and day", "People", "Purple", "To the broken land", "Soul", "Kishan", "Gozal", "Sezgi", "Diyorim", "Vijdon erki", "Kozgalish", "Khazon", "O'zbekim", "Qalandar ishqi", "Galdir", "Memory of the Road", "For the East", "Death of the Amir", "Desire for Freedom", "Am I a Poet?", "A Piece of Straw", "Rebellion of the Maid", "Love of Cholpon", Khalil farang ", " Autumn ", " Snow ", " What is literature? ", " Hijrat ", " Safarnoma ", " There is no return "(article) and others [5, 257].

Cholpon also made significant contributions to translation: Shakespeare's Hamlet, Gotsi's Turandot, Pushkin's Boris Gadunov, Dubrovsky, Gogol's The Investigator, Gorki's Mother, Fayko's Portfolio Man, Tretyakov's Scream, China! " He skillfully translated the Uzbek language into Uzbek.

But time did not spare Cholpon. He began to appear in the press in the 1930s, and in 1932 he was forced to move to Moscow. After returning from Moscow in 1935, he began working as a literary assistant at the Hamza Theater. But the stones thrown at Cholpon did not stop, he was arrested on July 13, 1937, and shot on October 4, 1938, the day before the verdict was announced.

The arrest of advanced, progressive intellectuals for the penitentiary authorities and their executioners, such as the State Political Administration (GPU), the People's Commissariat of Internal Affairs (NKVD), which at the time was the sharp sword and steel shield of the Center, was not allowed for their activities. q There was no question of fabricating accusations, of fabricating fabrications. Abdulla Qodiri, Abdurauf Fitrat, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Usmon Nosir, Elbek (Mashriq Yunusov), Mahmud Botu, Ghazi Yunus, who are the pillars of Uzbek literature and whose unique works have won the love of the people. On the basis of slander, he was physically destroyed as an "enemy of the people" and his brilliant activity was extinguished [6, 111].

In 1956, those who were persecuted in the 1930s began to be acquitted, including Cholpon. A five-member panel will be formed to study his creative heritage: Bahrom Rakhmonov - First Secretary of the Writers' Union - Chairman; members: Uygun, Mirzakalon Ismoilii, Gulom Karimov, Ozod Sharafiddinov [7, 426-427].

Cholpon's creative heritage has been praised by readers during the years of independence, and a collection of his best works, the collection of poems "I got my word again" was published in 1991 and the newly established Alisher Navoi Uzbekistan He was awarded the State Prize of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

In short, there is a certain notion in the memory of today's educated, mature young people of Uzbekistan, not only young people but also the elderly, that they are Jadids. This concept embodies figures who love their homeland and even sacrifice themselves to raise the consciousness of its people.

In order to perpetuate the memory of the victims of repressions, in 2000-2002 a memorial complex "Martyrs' Memory" and a museum "Memory of Victims of Repression" were built in Tashkent. The proclamation of August 31 as the Day of Remembrance of the Victims of Repression by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 1, 2001 testifies to the immortal traces of these people in the history of our country. The memory of Cholpon is one of those victims. We young people are proud of our ancestors and we follow their example.

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